

Working abstract

Supporting Small Farms in Marginal Areas: An Alternative Approach to EU agricultural payments

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Small farms play a crucial role in sustaining the environmental, social, and economic vitality of mountain areas, yet their definition and effective policy support remain ongoing challenges. In this study, farms are classified as small when their standard output is below a range of €20.000 and 30.000€. According to Census data, farms within this category constitute a substantial share of Italian agriculture, accounting for 81% of all farms in Italy. Their relevance is even more pronounced in mountainous regions, where small farms represent 82% of holdings and account for 61% of agricultural labour units.

Mountain farming plays a multifaceted role that extends well beyond food production, delivering key ecosystem functions such as water management, soil protection, biodiversity conservation, and carbon storage. It also supports the maintenance of rural heritage, long-standing agricultural practices, and locally rooted food networks. Nevertheless, agriculture in mountain regions is increasingly affected by structural pressures: farm numbers continue to shrink, generational turnover remains limited, and the likelihood of land abandonment is growing. These developments endanger the socio-economic resilience of rural areas and may undermine the future provision of ecosystem services in mountain landscapes

Current UE subsidies often fail to adequately support small mountain holdings. In Northern Italian mountains, only one third of farms receive EU subsidies, a proportion that decreases to less than one fourth among small farms. Such category is marginally benefitted by public European subsidies as they are provided on an area-based criterion.

To address this policy gap, this study proposes a payment tailored to small farms, in particular for those located in mountain/marginal areas. Unlike current EU financial support based on farmed land area, this one introduces an annual payment based on the amount of farm labour and conditioned to

minimum requirements on environmental and labour stability. Such kind of support aims at incentivizing a stable presence of farmers in mountain and marginal areas.

To assess farmers attitudes to participate in such a new support modality, a hypothetical experiment was conducted among small mountain farms in Northern Italy. The experimental setting tested the effect of environmental commitments (such as certain certifications) length of the labour-based payment contract and the amount of payment for labour unit on the likelihood of farmers would accept the new subsidy modality instead of the current area payment. The questionnaire was administered to 250 small farms (according to the economic size threshold indicated above) with a response rate of 70%, representing approximately 3% of mountain farms in the study region (located in northern Italy).

Results indicate that farmers are averse to environmental certification and longer contractual commitments, requiring higher payments per labour unit in order to accept them. Higher levels of payment per labour unit confirms that higher incentives increase farmers' willingness to engage in the new subsidy system. Furthermore, the interest in entering the new subsidy modality is lower among farmers that are beneficiaries of per-area payments, while is higher for that are not benefitted by EU agricultural payments.

To explore how small mountain farms might react to alternative forms of public support, a set of simulation exercises was conducted covering all holdings that fall within the target profile. The analysis considered three possible designs of the proposed scheme, each characterised by different levels of environmental engagement and varying lengths of contractual obligation. Findings suggest that the most demanding option—requiring both a formal environmental commitment and a multi-year agreement—would attract interest from only a limited share of farms, even when financial incentives are relatively substantial. Conversely, configurations with lighter requirements show markedly higher potential participation, particularly when the associated payment reaches the upper end of the tested range. Taken together, these results indicate that a support mechanism centred on labour involvement could broaden the access of small mountain farms to agricultural policy instruments, with positive implications for the long-term sustainability of mountain areas and the prevention of land abandonment.

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